

A novel NAC transcription factor gene, GhNAC20, regulates leaf senescence and diverse stress responses in cotton, *Gossypium hirsutum* L.

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Abstract

NAC (NAM, ATAF1, 2 and CUC2) transcription factors play crucial roles in various plant developmental processes and response to environmental stresses. In cotton, NAC family genes have been analyzed, however their specific function in leaf senescence has not been fully reported. In the present study, a gene encoding a NAC protein *GhNAC20* was cloned. Yeast-one Hybrid assay showed *GhNAC20* possess transcriptional activation activities which was located in the C-terminal region. Analysis by qRT-PCR indicated that *GhNAC20* was highly expressed in the cotyledon, true leaves and in senescing leaves compared to other tissues. To confirm its role in leaf senescence, the transcript levels were measured during natural and dark-induced senescence. Strikingly, *GhNAC20* was strongly upregulated during these types of senescence. In order to gain more insight into its function, *GhNAC20* was silenced in cotton plants by VIGS technique. *GhNAC20*-silenced plants showed delayed leaf senescence as knockdown mutants showed prolonged stay-green phenotypes. Promoter analysis revealed various *cis*-acting elements suggesting that *GhNAC20* could be involved in several response network regulations. ABA, JA, ET and SA signaling molecules which promote senescence, upregulated *GhNAC20* when exogenously applied to cotton seedling though each induced it at different times after treatments. These results indicate that a *GhNAC20* is a novel nuclear protein that promotes leaf senescence in cotton.

Keywords. Senescence, *Gossypium hirsutum* L. NAC, Stress responses.

Introduction

Leaf senescence is an age-dependent deterioration process at the cellular, tissue, organ, or organismal level, leading to death or the end of the life span (Gan and Amasino 1997; Lim et al. 2007). During senescence process, photosynthesis rate decreases accompanied by degradation of macromolecules eventually the cell integrity is lost. Leaf senescence has a negative impact on crop yield due to its limiting effect on the growth phase of crop plants (Lim et al. 2007; Fan et al. 2015). Understanding and manipulation of senescence process in crop plants would increase crop longevity, productivity, improve stress tolerance and reduce pre-or post-harvest spoilage (Ülker et al. 2007). Like any other developmental process, leaf senescence is regulated by both internal and external factors. Growth regulators such as Cytokinins, Abscisic acid (ABA), Salicylic acid (SA), Jasmonate (JA), Ethylene (ET), Nitric Oxide and Brassinosteroids as internal factors act in a precisely coordinated manner to mediate the process (Gepstein 2004) while external factors are environmental stresses: extreme temperature, shading, drought, wounding, nutrient limitation, pathogen attack and oxidative stress by UV-B irradiation and ozone. Leaf senescence as a complex process, involve orderly and sequential changes in the cellular physiology, biochemistry and gene expression (Breeze et al. 2011). Although considered to be a highly entropic process, the onset, progression and completion of leaf senescence requires extensive and orchestrated transcriptional reprogramming, de novo protein synthesis as well as post-translational regulation (Guo et al. 2004; Kong et al. 2013). Transcriptional reprogramming for gene expression and regulation involves transcriptional factors (TFs) which may activate or inhibit expression of downstream genes.

Being one of the largest plant TFs, NACs defined by NAM, ATF and CUC2 are plant-specific family of transcription factors widely involved in plant development processes and stress responses (Ooka et al. 2003; Guo et al. 2004). Since the first NAC gene, denoted NAM for no apical meristem was isolated from petunia, many NACs have been reported to contribute to various developmental processes such as shoot apical meristem development (Souer et al. 1996), lateral root development (He et al. 2005), senescence (Guo and Gan 2006) and secondary wall formation (Mitsuda et al. 2007). It has been demonstrated that many NAC family genes show enhanced expression during natural leaf senescence and dark-induced senescence in Arabidopsis (Guo and Gan 2006), and may play a central role in mediating leaf senescence. *GhNAC12* and

GhNAP in cotton play an important role in leaf senescence as they are upregulated during induced and natural leaf senescence, and overexpression of these genes accelerates leaf senescence (Fan et al. 2015; Zhao et al. 2015). *AtNAP* is strongly up-regulated during leaf senescence in Arabidopsis, and *atnap* null mutants show a delayed leaf senescence phenotype, whereas the inducible over-expression of *AtNAP* causes precocious leaf senescence (Guo and Gan 2006). Although it has been evidently illustrated that most of NAC members are play important role in leaf senescence, still large number of NACs remain functionally uncharacterized.

During leaf senescence, there exist a cross-talk between Environmental stresses and signaling pathways which trigger stress- responsible genes which in turn affect leaf senescence (Breeze et al. 2011; Yang et al. 2011; Zhang and Zhou 2013). It has been reported that any environmental stress with negative effect on growth conditions may induce or accelerate senescence in plants (Buchanan-Wollaston 2007). The stresses such as extreme temperature, drought, wounding, high salinity and low temperature positively affect senescence while triggering the production of signaling molecules. For example, phytohormone Abscisic acid (ABA) is produced during abiotic stress conditions such as drought and salinity (Kazuo et al.2011). ABA is a core mediator in controlling plant responses to abiotic stress by regulating stomatal closure and triggering many stress-related genes, thereby increasing the tolerance to plants stress. Many studies have revealed that JA and its derivatives play important role in regulating the response to leaf senescence in plants. JA-induced leaf senescence is accompanied by the increased expression of several enzymes involved in JA biosynthesis and the decreased expression of the genes involved in photosynthesis (Buchanan-Wollaston 2007). Additionally, NAC genes have been reported to simultaneously regulate both developmental and stress responses in plants. *AtNAC2*, a transcription factor downstream of ethylene and auxin signaling pathways, is simultaneously involved in salt stress response and lateral root development (He et al. 2005). Previous studies on NAC protein encoding genes in cotton indicate a few characterized genes with regard to senescence and stress responses (Shah et al. 2014; Fan et al. 2015; Zhao et al. 2015). Although 77 NAC genes in *Gossypium hirsutum* L. and 145 NAC genes in *G ramondii* Ulbr have been reported to respond to many stresses (Meng et al. 2009; Shah et al. 2014) ,only *GhNAC12* and *GhNAP* have been reported as positive regulator of leaf senescence in cotton (Fan et al. 2015; Zhao et al. 2015). Therefore identification of more cotton NAC genes would be useful to

understanding the mechanisms of leaf senescence and stress response in cotton.

In this study we performed functional analyses of an up-regulated *GhNAC20* gene during leaf senescence and characterized its role in plant stress responses. Silencing *GhNAC20* in cotton plants using Virus-induced gene silencing (VIGS) method resulted to delayed leaf senescence. Moreover, detached leaves from silenced plants showed slower chlorophyll degradation compared to control. Transcript levels for this gene confirmed that its knockdown could delay senescence in the cotton leaves. As a nuclear protein, it showed sensitivity to external stimuli and could be involved in regulation of these stimuli through senescence related signaling pathways. Our findings therefore, provide important information to understanding the role played by *GhNAC20* in cotton development and stress responses.

Materials and Methods

Plant materials

Cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L. cv CCRI-10) seedlings were grown in a growth chamber at 28°C under a 16 h light and 8 h dark photoperiod. Seedlings were harvested at three- and four-leaf stages, frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at –80°C for RNA extraction. For tissue specific analysis, cotyledon leaves, true leaves, stem, root, flower parts and 10 DAP fiber were collected from field and stored for later use. Seven-day-old cotton seedlings were used for the various treatments.

For exogenous application of hormone solutions, leaves of uniformly developed seedlings were irrigated with 2 mM SA, 100 uM ABA, 100 µM methyl Jasmonate (MeJA) and 100uM Ethylene (ET). For salinity and drought treatments, the seedlings were treated with 200 mM NaCl or 15% (w/v) PEG6000 respectively. For hydrogen peroxide (H₂O₂) and wounding, Seedling were sprayed with 20mM H₂O₂ and wounds inflicted by injuring three leaves from the top. After each treatment samples from treated and control were frozen in liquid nitrogen and stored at –80°C for further analysis. For reliability of the results, each experiment was repeated at least twice.

To analyze the progression of natural senescence, *Gossypium hirsutum* L. cv CCRI-10 was field-grown under natural conditions during the summer of 2015 in Anyang (Henan province, China). Leaves from these plants were harvested at five developmental stages defined by severity of visible symptoms and by determination of total chlorophyll content, from non-senescent leaf

stage (NS) to completely senescent stage (CS) approximately 90% yellowing of the leaf surface (Shah et al. 2014). At each senescent stage RNA was isolated for qRT-PCR Analysis. Further natural senescence was monitored on the cotyledon leaves from the first week after germination. Cotyledon leaf samples for nine weeks were collected from the field, their morphological changes noted and then frozen for transcript measurement. For dark-induced senescence, detached leaves were submerged in water and incubated in the dark for four days at room temperature.

Total RNA isolation and cDNA synthesis

Total RNA was extracted using hot borate method with few modifications (Hunter and Reid 2001) and treated with DNase I digestion using RNAPrep Pure Plant Kit (Tiangen China) to eliminate the potential genomic DNA contamination. The RNA concentration and purity were determined by gel electrophoresis and Nano-drop spectrophotometer. The cDNA for cloning work was synthesized from the RNA extracted from leaves using 5X All-In-One RT MasterMix (ABM- Canada) according to manufacturer's protocol. The RT-PCR was set as follows; 25°C for 10min, 42°C for 50min and 85°C for 5mins then put in ice for a few minutes. The newly synthesized strand cDNA was stored at -20°C. To prepare cDNA for RT-qPCR, 2 µg of total RNA was reverse-transcribed using the ReverTra Ace qPCR RT kit (TOYOBO, Japan). The final cDNA products were diluted 150-fold with RNAase free water prior to use.

Full-length of *GhNAC20* gene

The cDNA (Accession No. KC847197) earlier deposited in the NCBI database by our lab (Shah et al. 2014) was used to design primers for *GhNAC20*. An ORF of 846-bp was amplified from CCRI-10, ligated to simple T-vector (pMD18-T Vector) and sequenced by GENEWIZ (Beijing, China). Primers were designed with Oligo 6.0 and are shown in Table.1

Multiple Sequence Alignment and Phylogenetic Analysis

Homology searches were performed using Arabidopsis database (<https://www.arabidopsis.org>) and NCBI Blast program (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/BLAST>). Translation of nucleotide sequences for the obtained homologues was done using ExpASy online program (<http://web.expasy.org/translate/>) and alignment conducted by ClustalW2 program

(<http://www.ebi.ac.uk/Tools/msa/clustalw2/>) . Phylogenetic analysis was employed to investigate the evolutionary relationships between *GhNAC20* and other NAC proteins. A Neighbor joining tree was generated by MEGA 5.0 (Tamura et al. 2007). A bootstrap analysis with 1,000 replicates was performed to assess the statistical reliability of the tree topology

Bioinformatics analysis for GhNAC20

Open reading frame and protein prediction were made using NCBI ORF Finder (<http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/gorf/gorf.html>). The theoretical isoelectric point (pI) and mass values for mature peptides were calculated using the Peptide-Mass program (<http://us.expasy.org/tools/peptide-mass.html>) while protein subcellular localization was predicted using WoLF PSORT (<http://wolfpsort.org/>). In order to investigate the Genomic structure of *GhNAC20* ,Gene structure display server (GSDS) program (<http://gsds.cbi.pku.edu.cn/>) (Hu et al. 2015) was used to illustrate exon/intron organization by comparing the cDNA with its corresponding genomic DNA sequences obtained from cotton genome project database (<http://cgp.genomics.org.cn/>). The structures of the cotton *GhNAC20* protein was analyzed by Motifscan (http://myhits.isbsib.ch/cgi-bin/motif_scan).

Promoter Analysis

Total genomic DNA was extracted from cotton leaf using the CTAB method (Permingeat et al. 1998) and used as template to clone the promoter. 1500bp upstream region of *GhNAC20* was amplified by PCR using region specific primers (table.1). The PCR products were purified, linked to T-Vector and sequenced. The promoter sequence was then searched online PlantCARE database (<http://bioinformatics.psb.ugent.be/webtools/plantcare/html/>) to investigate the putative cis-acting elements.

Expression Analysis of GhNAC20

The cDNA was synthesized from 2ug of RNA from various samples in a 20 reaction volume using ReverTra Ace qPCR RT kit (TOYOBO, Japan) according to the manufacturer's manual. Relative expression levels of genes in each sample were normalized to the expression level of *GhActin1*. PCR products were detected by SYBR Green I fluorescence dye (Takara, china) in the Applied Biosystems 7500/7500 Faster Real- Time PCR system Machine. The following thermal

cycle conditions were used: 95°C for 2 min, followed by 40 cycles of 95°C for 5 s, products collected at 60°C for 34 s. All reactions were performed in triplicate. Following the PCR, a melting curve analysis was performed. Ct or threshold cycle was used for relative quantification of the input target number (Livak and Schmittgen 2001). Relative fold difference (N) is the number of treated target gene transcript copies relative to that of the untreated gene transcript copies, and was calculated as follows:

$$N = 2^{-\Delta\Delta Ct} = 2^{(\Delta Ct_{\text{treated}} - \Delta Ct_{\text{control}})}$$

Where $\Delta\Delta Ct = \Delta Ct$ of the treated sample minus ΔCt of the untreated control sample, and ΔCt is the difference in threshold cycles for *GhNAC20* target and the *GhActin* internal reference.

Plasmid construction for VIGS Assay and vector inoculation

Specific fragments approximately 300 bp (Guo et al. 2011; Bello et al. 2014) were amplified via PCR and cloned into the T-simple vector according to the manufacturer's specifications (Takara China). Primers used are shown in table.1. The resulting clones were confirmed by sequencing. The T-vector plasmids carrying gene fragments were digested using the restriction enzymes *speI* and *ascI* and were subsequently inserted into the multiple cloning site of pCLCrVA vector to produce pCLCrVA:*GhNAC20*. The plasmids pCLCrVB , pCLCrVA and their derivatives pCLCrVA:*GhNAC20* and pCLCrVA: *CHLI* were individually transformed into *Agrobacterium tumefaciens* strain LBA4404 according to Gu 2014 (Gu et al. 2014). The cotton seedlings of two weeks old were injected with the infiltrate carrying the plasmids. The inoculated plants were maintained in a growth chamber at 23°C for effective viral infection and spreading.

Transcriptional activation activity of *GhNAC20*

To investigate whether GhNAC20 has transcriptional activities the entire or partial coding regions of *GhNAC20* were obtained by PCR using fragment specific primers (table1).The PCR products were inserted into the *EcoRI* and *BamHI* site of pGBKT7 vector, containing the GAL4 DNA binding domain to obtain pGBKT7:GhNAC20-F, GBKT7:GhNAC20-N, and GBKT7:GhhNAC20-C. The three constructs and GBKT7 vector (negative control) were transformed into the yeast strain Y187 (clontech), plated and incubated for three days.

Measurement of chlorophyll content

Chlorophyll content was extracted from cotton leaves samples (from the same samples used for RNA extraction) using 80% acetone method (Djanaguiraman et al. 2011). Cotton leaves (0.2g) were incubated in 20 ml 80% acetone in the dark at 4°C. After 48hrs the supernatant was photometrically measured at optical density absorbance 649nm and 665nm. Total chlorophyll content was calculated using the equation $((OD_{665nm} \times 13.95 - OD_{649nm} \times 6.88) + (OD_{649nm} \times 24.96 - OD_{665nm} \times 7.32)) / (\text{weight of sample})$. Each sample was measured three times, and the mean results were used.

Experimental design and statistical analysis

The data obtained were subjected to descriptive statistical analysis and were expressed as the means and standard error (SE) of at least three replicates. All experimental data were presented as the means of at least three independent replicates, and the analysis for significance was performed using Student's T-test at $P \leq 0.05$. Error bars shown in all figures represent standard deviation.

Results

Characterization and bioinformatics analysis of GhNAC20

GhNAC20 gene was isolated from cotton *G. hirsutum* (CCRI 10) using gene specific primers (Table.1). The full-length cDNA (GeneBank Accession No. KC847197) was 1132bp with an ORF of 846bp, encoding 281 amino acids with a molecular weight of 36.6kDa and a theoretical isoelectric point of 8.40. Using WoLF PSORT program, *GhNAC20* was predicted to be located in the nucleus, confirming its role as a nuclear transcription factor. In order to investigate genomic organization, the genomic sequence and the cDNA sequence were compared using GSDS server (Hu et al. 2015). Like most of NAC family members, *GhNAC20* had three exons and two introns. Additionally the NAC domain stretched within 16-162aa. (Ooka et al. 2003).

To predict the function of *GhNAC20* we constructed Phylogenetic tree using protein sequences from other plant species (Figure.1b). Multiple sequence alignments of the full-length protein sequences, including the highly conserved N-terminal NAM domain and the divergent C-terminal activation domain, were performed by ClustalW program (fig.1a). It was earlier established that *GhNAC20* belongs to NAC-III subfamily (Shah et al. 2014). Some of these

members have been reported to be involved in stress related responses and senescence (Meng et al. 2007). *GhNAC20* showed high homology to *ANAC036* (54.4%), *GmNAC6*(62.1%) and *CarNAC67*(87%). Based on this similarity we proposed that *GhNAC20* could be involved in leaf senescence in cotton.

Figure.1. Phylogenetic tree and Comparison of the deduced amino acid sequence of *GhNAC20* with other NAC domain proteins from other species. **a.** Multiple alignment of putative amino acids sequence of *GhNAC20* and other NAC protein domains. Identical amino acids are shaded in black, and similar amino acids are shaded in gray **b.** Phylogenetic tree with *GhNAC20* marked with black triangle

GhNAC20 is significantly expressed in the leaves

To investigate the physiological role played by *GhNAC20* in cotton, the expression levels of *GhNAC20* in different organs were determined by qRT-PCR. *GhNAC20* was preferentially expressed in the cotyledon, young and senescing leaves. Moderate expression was observed in the root, petals and stamens while stem, sepals, pistil and 10DPA fiber exhibited low expression levels (Fig.2). The abundance of this gene in almost all organs indicated that it may have a major

role in plant growth and development with preference to leaf senescence.

Fig.2. Organ-specific expression of *GhNAC20* in cotton (*G. hirsutum L.*) CCRI10 cultivar

***GhNAC20* is expressed during natural and induced senescence**

The result from tissue specific expression showed that *GhNAC20* was highly expressed in the senescing leaves. To confirm its involvement in leaf senescence we decided to investigate its expression trend during natural and dark-induced senescence. Meanwhile we measured chlorophyll content to verify senescence progress (Fig.3c). For natural senescence, qRT-PCR analysis showed that the expression level of *GhNAC20* in mature leaves increased steadily from NS (non-senescence) to CS (complete senescence) (Fig.3a,b). The same was observed in the cotyledons leaves senescence (Fig.3d). The expression of *GhCAB*, a negative marker gene for senescence confirmed the expected opposite expression level while *GhNAP*, a positive marker gene showed consistency with *GhNAC20* (fig.3e,f) implying that *GhNAC20*, positively regulates leaf senescence. For dark-induced senescence, detached leaves at same developmental stage were uprightly submerged in water and incubated for 7 days at room temperature. *GhNAC20* expression level strongly increased peaking at the 5day indicating that this gene was induced by light-starved environment (Fig.3g). Our results suggest that *GhNAC20* could play an important role in the regulation of leaf senescence in cotton.

3c.

3a

3b

3d.

3e.

Fig.3 Expression patterns of GhNAC20 during natural and dark-induced senescence in reference to marker genes.

a. Expression level of GhNAC20 during progression of natural senescence as marked from NS leaf to CS leaf. **b.** Morphological changes from NS leaf to CS leaf, whereas NS non-senescent leaf, IS initial-senescent leaf (15 % yellow), ES early senescent leaf (30 % yellow), LS late-senescent leaf (50 % yellow), CS completely senescent leaf (90 % yellow). **c.** Chlorophyll content decrease from NS leaf to CS leaf. **d-f** show expression of GhNAC20 during cotyledon senescence as compared with Marker genes for senescence (GhCAB and GhNAP). **g.** Shows expression level of GhNAC20 during 7 days dark-induced leaves senescence. Bars indicate standard deviation.

Knockdown of GhNAC20 in cotton delays leaf senescence

To further investigate the function of GhNAC20 in regulation of leaf senescence, we employed Virus induced gene silencing (VIGS) approach. This technique utilizes cotton leaf crumple virus (CLCrV)-based vector coupled with *Agrobacterium*-mediated infiltration system to study gene function in cotton (Gu et al. 2014). VIGS induces loss of function of a phenotype of a particular gene, these avoids a long and difficult process of plant regeneration (Liu et al. 2002). To avoid silencing other NAC family members in cotton we chose 300-bp fragment from highly diverged C-terminus region of GhNAC20. The fragment was inserted into pCLCrVA and co-infiltrated into cotton seedlings with *Agrobacterium* carrying pCLCrVA: GhNAC20. The control plants were infiltrated with a vector without the fragment. CCRI-10 cultivars were used for VIGS assays. By 20 days post infiltration (dpi), cotton plants infiltrated with *Agrobacterium* carrying pCLCrVA-CHL1 and pCLCrVB showed photo-bleaching (Albino phenotype) in newly emerging true leaves, an indication of gene-silencing system efficiency. By 30dpi GhNAC20-silenced plants were confirmed by PCR and labeled as silenced(S) while control plants were labeled as VA. qRT-

PCR analysis revealed that the transcript levels of *GhNAC20* in silenced plants were approximately 68% lower than the control plants (fig. 4a). By 65 dpi the first true leaf of the control plant showed yellowing (loss of chlorophyll) but no visible yellowing was observed in the *GhNAC20*-silenced plants (fig.4b,c,d). Additionally three leaves counted from the shoot-down, from both the *GhNAC20*-silenced plants and control plants were incubated in the dark for four days. Transcript level of *GhNAC20* in *GhNAC20*-silenced leaves was relatively lower than control plants (fig.4e). These results taken together indicated that knockdown of *GhNAC20* delays leaf senescence in cotton

Fig.4. Silencing *GhNAC20* gene in cotton and its transcript levels in silenced plants. **a.** Relative expression level of *GhNAC20* in the silenced selected plants (S2-3) and non-silenced plants (VA and cultivar CCR110). **b.** Phenotypes of silenced and non-silenced plants after 65 days. Arrows indicate the yellowing on the non-silenced/control plant and also show control and silenced plants. **c.** Relative expression level of *GhNAC20* in silenced and non-silenced leaves incubated in the dark for 4days. The values are presented as the means of three biological replicates

***GhNAC20* Promoter analysis**

Expression of stress-responsive NACs may be tightly regulated by several stress-responsive regulatory elements contained in the promoter region (Puranik et al. 2012). To investigate further function of *GhNAC20* we cloned 1500bp fragment upstream region of *GhNAC20*. Analysis of this region by PlantCARE revealed presence of many putative cis-regulatory element binding motifs. These elements included TATA, pathogen/elicitor-related elements, Box-W1, Box I, multiple abiotic and biotic stress responsive elements including one salicylic acid and ethylene-responsive elements. Presences of these elements imply that *GhNAC20* plays a role in the plant response to biotic and abiotic stress

***GhNAC20* is induced by phytohormones**

Phytohormones play significant role in the regulation of plant development processes against abiotic and biotic stress. These signaling molecules play a vital roles in mediating the expression of downstream genes related to plant development processes (Buchanan-Wollaston et al. 2005). To determine whether the expression of *GhNAC20* can be induced by well-known senescence promoting signaling molecules, seven-day old cotton seedlings were exogenously treated with ABA, MeJA, SA or ET. The result of these treatments showed that all the four molecules were able to induce the expression of *GhNAC20*. However, the induction time and strength varied among the four phytohormones. For instance, SA and ABA steadily maintained high expression levels of *GhNAC20* from 6h, reaching their maximum at 24h and 36h while MeJA and ET slowly induced it but peaked at the 36h after treatment (Fig.5a-d). The result indicated that *GhNAC20* is responsive to exogenously applied senescence signaling molecules and could be involved in signal pathways during leaf senescence.

Fig.5 Expression patterns of *GhNAC20* in response to chemical stress within 48h of treatment. **a.** 2mM SA treatment, **b.** 100 μ M MeJA treatment **c.** 100 μ M Ethylene treatment. **d.** 100 μ M ABA treatment. Total RNA was isolated at indicated times after treatment for qPCR analysis. *GhActin* was used as standard control in the experiments. Error bars indicate Standard deviations.

Response of *GhNAC20* to abiotic stresses.

To test whether *GhNAC20* is involved in plant responses to abiotic stress, the transcripts levels were measured by qRT-PCR in the treated two-week old cotton seedlings. Cotton seedlings were exposed to drought (PEG6000), salt (NaCl), low temperature (4°C), H₂O₂ and wounding. For the dehydration treatment, *GhNAC20* was steadily upregulated, while salt stress induced *GhNAC20* rapidly at the 12h and gradually declined (Fig.6a). Wounding and H₂O₂ treatment sharply

induced *GhNAC20* at 2h but significantly decreased throughout the indicated time (Fig.6b-c). There was no significant change in *GhNAC20* transcript level upon exposure to cold stress (Fig.6d).

Fig.6 Expression patterns of GhNAC20 under abiotic stress treatments on two-week old cotton seedlings a. Drought stress with 15% PEG 6000 and 200 mM NaCl (salt) stress treatments. b wounding uniformly selected leaves. c Hydrogen peroxide (20mM H₂O₂) treatment. d. Cold (4°C) treatment

Transcriptional activation activity of *GhNAC20*

Several NACs not only act on gene promoters but also have activation activity on the downstream genes (Hu et al. 2008). According to Ooka .2003 (Ooka et al. 2003) NAC family proteins possess transcriptional activation region at the C-terminus. To examine whether *GhNAC20* has transcriptional activation activity, the N- (146aa) and C-(135aa) terminal fragments as well as the full-length *GhNAC20* were fused to the GAL4 DBD of the pGBKT7 vector. The resulting constructs and the negative vector control pGBKT7 were transformed into Y187 yeast strain and incubated for 3 days. All of the transformants grew well on SD/- Trp/ medium, but only the yeast cells containing the pGBKT7- GhNAC20 and pGBKT7-GhNAC20-C plasmids grew and turned blue on SD/-Trp/X- α -Gal/ (Fig.7). These results indicated that *GhNAC20*, has transcriptional activation activity in the C-terminus

Fig.7. Transactivation activity of *GhNAC20*. Three constructs: GBKT7-GhNAC20 -F, GBKT7- GhNAC20 -N, and GBKT7- GhNAC20 -C.) and GBKT7 vector (negative control) were transformed into the yeast strain Y187 plated and incubated for three days .All yeast cells containing the plasmids grew well into white colonies in SD/-Trp medium, but only yeast cell containing GBKT7- GhNAC20 -F and GBKT7- GhNAC20 -C turned blue in SD/-Trp/- α -Gal medium

Discussion

NACs have been isolated and characterized from other plant species (Lin et al. 2007; Mao et al.

2014; Ning et al. 2015). In cotton there are 77 putative NAC proteins that have been reported (Shah et al. 2014). To date only two genes (*GhNAC12* and *GhNAP*) have been demonstrated to regulate leaf senescence in cotton (Fan et al. 2015; Zhao et al. 2015) yet it has been proved that NAC transcription factors (TFs) represent a large fraction of the senescence regulated genes in many plant species including cotton (Balazadeh et al. 2010). Short season cotton for example CCRI 10 is accompanied with premature leaf senescence which could be possibly regulated by NAC family genes among other factors. In the present study we investigated the role played by *GhNAC20* in regulating leaf senescence using VIGS method and analyzing its sensitivity to senescence inducing factors. Our findings not only add a new characterized member to the list of cotton NACs, but also extend our understanding on the biological functions of cotton NACs.

Phylogenetic analysis revealed that *GhNAC20* shares conserved NAC domain (Aida et al. 1997) with other characterized NAC TFs. The NAC family genes normally encode proteins with approximately 300aa (Kikuchi et al. 2000) this imply that they could have similar functions. *GhNAC20* showed homology to *ANAC036*(54.4%), *GmNAC6*(62.1%) and *CarNAC67*(87%). *ANAC036* was highly expressed during leaf senescence and causes dwarfism phenotype in Arabidopsis (Kato et al. 2010) while *GmNAC6* is associated with senescence or cell death in soya beans (Faria et al. 2011). This identity suggest that, *GhNAC20* could play the same role in cotton. *CarNAC67* has not been characterized, and therefore functional analysis of *GhNAC20* could be fundamental in characterization of *CarNAC67*. Like many other members of NAC TFs, *GhNAC20* has three exons and two introns with UTR on the upstream of coding region. Additionally, majority of NACs are localized in the nucleus which ensure that downstream genes are activated or repressed (Fujita et al. 2004; Peng et al. 2009). Similarly, *GhNAC20* was found to be localized in nucleus with transcriptional activation activities that were mapped into its C-terminal region (Fig.7). This indicated that *GhNAC20* is a NAC protein localized in the nucleus and may function as transcriptional activator in cotton.

It has been reported that several plant NAC family genes are tissue-specific (Lin et al. 2007; Meng et al. 2009). Rice *OsNAC5* and *OsNAC3* are expressed in root and leaf respectively and this could mean that they play important role in these organs (Kikuchi et al. 2000). *GhNAC20* was constitutively expressed in all the tissues under investigation, however high expression was recorded in the senescing, cotyledon and true leaves (Fig.2). This high expression implied that *GhNAC20* plays a major role in leaf development especially regulation of leaf senescence. To

confirm this, we decided to investigate its involvement in natural and induced leaf senescence. Leaf senescence as final stage of leaf development it is highly regulated and genetically programmed. During this process SAGs are usually upregulated during senescence, and if a SAG is induced solely in response to natural senescence then it is likely to function directly in the senescence program (Weaver et al. 1998). In the present study, *GhNAC20* was highly expressed in naturally senescing leaves marked from NS to CS suggesting that it was induced by senescence and its involvement in this process cannot be overemphasized. As a positive regulator for senescence, *GhNAC20* transcripts accumulated increasingly as the leaves became more yellow, an indicator of senescence process (fig.3a,b). The same results were obtained from the cotyledon leaves (fig.3d). In this regard *GhNAC20* qualified as a SAG and may play a primary role in leaf senescence. Leaf senescence can be induced by light-starved conditions and previously, NAC family members have been upregulated by such stress (Lin and Wu 2004; Fukao et al. 2012). During our investigation, leaves were incubated in the dark and as senescence became more severe, the expression level of *GhNAC20* increased accordingly (fig.3g) suggesting that this gene was actively induced to participate in senescence process. Chlorophyll loss, a marker for senescence phenotypes (Liang et al. 2014), indicated the transition of leaf development state at phenotypic level (Hörtensteiner and Feller 2002; Gepstein 2004) and therefore its measure confirmed senescence process in the incubated leaves (Fig.3c). These results taken together demonstrated that *GhNAC20* is a SAG that plays role in both natural and dark-induced senescence.

Further we generated knockdown (silenced) plants based on VIGs approach and analyzed both the phenotypes and transcript level. VIGS, a molecular approach, has been used to study gene function by knocking down target genes (Liu et al. 2002; Gu et al. 2014). The CLCrV-VIGS system has been demonstrated to have high efficiency and long persistence in silencing genes in plants. To ascertain the system efficiency in cotton, *CHL*-gene silencing phenotype was used to represent the ideal visual marker for endogenous gene silencing efficiency due to its involvement in chloroplast development, as its loss of function results in an albino phenotype in true leaves (Gu et al. 2014). The same approach has been previously applied in the analysis of gene function in rice disease resistance *ONAC122* and *ONAC131* genes (Sun et al. 2013). In the present study *GhNAC20*-silenced plants showed delayed leaf senescence while in the control plants showed apparent yellowing (fig.4b,c ,d). Yellowing on control plant leaves, marked as V

appeared as they were approaching 65 days. While the cotyledon leaves in control plants became yellow and fell off, some of the silenced plants cotyledons were intact. The delay in yellowing or loss of chlorophyll was attributed to approximately 68% knockdown of *GhNAC20* in silenced plants (fig4b). Leaves from both plants, silenced and control incubated in the light-starved environment, indicated that expression level of *GhNAC20* was all lower in silenced plants than control (fig.4e). whereas darkness induced senescence, the knockdown of *GhNAC20* delayed yellowing in the silenced leaves reducing its expression level. This implied that *GhNAC20* was a positive regulator of leaf senescence in cotton consistent with its transcript accumulation in the control plants. It was clear that a knockdown of *GhNAC20* could delay leaf senescence in cotton and its mutants are likely to show a stay-green phenotype.

Phytohormones are important regulators of plant leaf senescence and that many altered senescence phenotypes occur as a result of altered hormone signaling (Li et al. 2012). Some of these signaling molecules such as ABA, JA, ET and SA promote senescence in plants while others like cytokinin inhibit senescence (Kikuchi et al. 2000; Fujita et al. 2004). Recently, it has been revealed that exogenous application of these signaling molecules induce several SAGs (Zeevaart and Creelman 1988; Weaver et al. 1998). In our study we examined the expression patterns of *GhNAC20* in the two-week cotton seedling treated with these signal molecules and we found that *GhNAC20* was induced by ET, ABA, JA, and SA. For example, ET upregulated *GhNAC20* gradually and peaked at 36h post infiltration, a time considered as late senescence. According to Abeles.1992, exogenous application of ethylene to plants induce senescence associated gene (SAGs) (Abeles et al. 1992.) at the same time ET is considered as a late inducer of SAGs and generally accelerates leaf senescence (Lim et al. 2007; Zhang and Zhou 2013) suggesting that there is a cross-talk between *GhNAC20* and ET during leaf senescence. Our findings confirmed that *GhNAC20* is involved in leaf senescence through ethylene pathway consistent with previous studies on NACs.

ABA as a key hormone mediating plant responses to environmental stress, it has been reported to promote leaf senescence and abscission when exogenously applied (Zeevaart and Creelman 1988; Finkelstein and Rock 2002; Adie et al. 2007). ABA rapidly induces the senescence syndrome and expression of several SAGs (Weaver et al. 1998; Gepstein 2004) which are consistent with its effects on leaf senescence. During leaf senescence, genes associated with ABA synthesis and signaling are up-regulated and the endogenous ABA level increases (Weaver et al.

1998; Graaff et al. 2006). To determine whether *GhNAC20* is induced by ABA, we treated cotton plants with ABA and apparently, like other senescence associated NACs, *GhNAC20* was steadily upregulated (Fig.5d) implying that *GhNAC20* is either involved in ABA synthesis or ABA signaling pathway during leaf senescence. ABA appears to be controlling activities of both cellular protection activities and senescence activities, thus *GhNAC20* may be induced to assist this reaction during senescence hence its role in leaf senescence.

As plant growth regulators, JA control many plant developmental and growth processes and mediate plant responses to abiotic and biotic stresses. Exogenous application of JA induces senescence and seem to control numerous expression of senescence related genes (Rao et al. 2000; Kim et al. 2009). *GhNAC20* was induced by JA and reached its peak at the 36 hpi (Fig.5c), this indicated that *GhNAC20* was under the control of JA signaling pathway as senescence progressed. Further, gradual increase of transcript level of this gene concurs with the fact that JA is not essential at the onset and progression of senescence but its effects are strong at the late stages of the process. We concluded that *GhNAC20* is important in JA signaling pathway involved in leaf senescence.

High levels of SA in senescing leaves tend to up-regulate SAGs during senescence whereas endogenous SA levels are fourfold higher in senescing leaves than non-senescing leaves (Morris et al. 2000). SA-deficient plants have shown reduced or undetected expression of SAGs with these plants showing delay in yellowing and reduced necrosis. A Transcriptome analysis of senescing Arabidopsis leaves from wild-type plants and SA-deficient *NahG* mutants revealed that many SAGs are dependent on the SA signaling pathway (Buchanan-Wollaston et al. 2005). In our study *GhNAC20* was upregulated with the application of SA to cotton seedlings (fig.5a). The high level of transcripts were maintained qualifying this gene as SAG with a close relationship with SA signaling pathway. The inducement of *GhNAC20* by SA indicated that *GhNAC20* is a SAG and could be involved in SA signaling network during senescence.

During leaf senescence, there exist a cross-talk between environmental stresses especially abiotic stress and signaling pathways which trigger stress- responsible genes which in turn affect leaf senescence (Breeze et al. 2011; Yang et al. 2011; Zhang and Zhou 2013). It has been reported that any environmental stress with negative effect on growth conditions may induce or accelerate senescence in plants (Zhang and Zhou 2013). The stresses such as extreme temperature, drought wounding, high salinity and low temperature positively affect senescence while triggering the

production of signaling molecules. The accumulation of these molecules may lead to regulation of SAGs. For example under stress ABA levels increase in the leaves inducing senescence thus upregulation of ABA-dependent SAGs (Gepstein and Thimann 1980). In our study *GhNAC20* was induced when seedlings were exposed to drought and high salt. While H₂O₂ upregulated *GhNAC20*, cold did not show significant changes of *GhNAC20* expression. Interestingly, Wounding rapidly and transiently upregulated *GhNAC20* at 2h (Fig.6b-c) implying that *GhNAC20* is a potential early regulator in the abiotic stress response. *GhNAC20* induction by SA and ET complement the fact that this gene is properly involved in response to biotic stress since SA and Et are crucial signaling regulators in biotic stress pathways (Glazebrook 2001; Glazebrook 2005; Peng et al. 2010). Previous studies have shown that abiotic stress responses may also share common components, indicating a crosstalk between abiotic and biotic stress signal transduction. These together demonstrate that *GhNAC20* may contribute to both abiotic and biotic stress responses in cotton. Evidence has accumulated on the fact that transcription factors generally are involved in plant development and stress response concurrently (Nakashima et al. 2012). For example *CarNAC1*, *GhNAC12* are simultaneously involved in stress responses and regulation of senescence (Peng et al. 2010; Shah et al. 2014; Zhao et al. 2015). Our study has shown that *GNAC20* is responsive to not only leaf senescence but also to exogenous stimuli such as wounding, salt and drought suggesting that *GhNAC20* transcription factor may also be a common mediator of the molecular mechanism of leaf senescence and stress responses.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we provide insight into how *GhNAC20*, as positive regulator for senescence, interact with environmental stresses to regulate leaf senescence in cotton. Overall our results indicate that *GhNAC20* is involved in leaf senescence regulation and abiotic stress responses. With senescence reducing the yield from cotton each season, the molecular and genetic manipulation of *GhNAC20* will be of great importance for production of relatively stay-green cultivars of cotton and in return it would have positive effect on cotton yield.

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Conflict of interest

The authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Authors' contributions

PK and EO designed the experiments. GO amended the manuscript. EO performed the experiments wrote the manuscript, generated graphs and collected experimental materials. All the authors read and approved the final manuscript.

Reference

- Adie BAT, Perez-Perez J, Perez-Perez MM, et al (2007) ABA Is an Essential Signal for Plant Resistance to Pathogens Affecting JA Biosynthesis and the Activation of Defenses in Arabidopsis. *Plant Cell Online* 19:1665–1681. doi: 10.1105/tpc.106.048041
- Aida M, Ishida T, Fukaki H, et al (1997) Genes involved in organ separation in Arabidopsis: an analysis of the cup-shaped cotyledon mutant. *Plant Cell* 9:841–57. doi: 10.1105/tpc.9.6.841
- Balazadeh S, Siddiqui H, Allu AD, et al (2010) A gene regulatory network controlled by the NAC transcription factor ANAC092/AtNAC2/ORE1 during salt-promoted senescence. *Plant J* 62:250–264. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-313X.2010.04151.x
- Bello B, Zhang X, Liu C, et al (2014) Cloning of *Gossypium hirsutum* Sucrose Non-Fermenting 1-Related Protein Kinase 2 Gene (GhSnRK2) and Its Overexpression in Transgenic Arabidopsis Escalates Drought and Low Temperature Tolerance. *PLoS One* 9:e112269. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0112269
- Breeze E, Harrison E, McHattie S, et al (2011) High-Resolution Temporal Profiling of Transcripts during Arabidopsis Leaf Senescence Reveals a Distinct Chronology of Processes and Regulation. *Plant Cell* 23:873–894. doi: 10.1105/tpc.111.083345
- Buchanan-Wollaston V (2007) Senescence processes in plants. *Annual Plant Reviews*, Volume 26. *Ann Bot* 101:197–197. doi: 10.1093/aob/mcm286
- Buchanan-Wollaston V, Page T, Harrison E, et al (2005) Comparative transcriptome analysis reveals significant differences in gene expression and signalling pathways between developmental and dark/starvation-induced senescence in Arabidopsis. *Plant J* 42:567–585. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-313X.2005.02399.x
- Djanaguiraman M, Prasad PV V, Al-Khatib K (2011) Ethylene perception inhibitor 1-MCP decreases oxidative damage of leaves through enhanced antioxidant defense mechanisms in soybean plants grown under high temperature stress. *Environ Exp Bot* 71:215–223. doi: 10.1016/j.envexpbot.2010.12.006
- Fan K, Bibi N, Gan S, et al (2015) A novel NAP member GhNAP is involved in leaf senescence in *Gossypium hirsutum*. *J Exp Bot* 66:4669–4682. doi: 10.1093/jxb/erv240
- Faria JAQA, Reis PAB, Reis MTB, et al (2011) The {NAC} domain-containing protein, {GmNAC}6, is a downstream component of the {ER} stress- and osmotic stress-induced {NRP}-mediated cell-death signaling pathway. *BMC Plant Biol* 11:129. doi: 10.1186/1471-

- Finkelstein RR, Rock CD (2002) Abscisic Acid Biosynthesis and Response. *Arab B* 1:e0058. doi: 10.1199/tab.0058
- Fujita M, Fujita Y, Maruyama K, et al (2004) A dehydration-induced NAC protein, RD26, is involved in a novel ABA-dependent stress-signaling pathway. *Plant J* 39:863–876. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-313X.2004.02171.x
- Fukao T, Yeung E, Bailey-Serres J (2012) The submergence tolerance gene, SUB1A, delays leaf senescence under prolonged darkness through hormonal regulation in rice. *Plant Physiol* 160:1795–1807. doi: 10.1104/pp.112.207738
- Gan S, Amasino RM (1997) Making sense of senescence: Molecular genetic regulation and manipulation of leaf senescence. *Plant Physiol* 113:313–319. doi: 10.1104/pp.113.2.313
- Gepstein S (2004) Leaf senescence--not just a “wear and tear” phenomenon. *Genome Biol* 5:212. doi: 10.1186/gb-2004-5-3-212
- Gepstein S, Thimann K V (1980) Changes in the abscisic acid content of oat leaves during senescence. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 77:2050–2053. doi: 10.1073/pnas.77.4.2050
- Glazebrook J (2001) Genes controlling expression of defense responses in Arabidopsis--2001 status. *Curr Opin Plant Biol* 4:301–308. doi: 10.1016/S1369-5266(00)00177-1
- Glazebrook J (2005) Contrasting Mechanisms of Defense Against Biotrophic and Necrotrophic Pathogens. *Annu Rev Phytopathol* 43:205–227. doi: 10.1146/annurev.phyto.43.040204.135923
- Graaff E Van Der, Schwacke R, Schneider A, et al (2006) Transcription Analysis of Arabidopsis Membrane Transporters and Hormone Pathways during Developmental and Induced Leaf Senescence 1 [W]. 141:776–792. doi: 10.1104/pp.106.079293.Leaf
- Gu Z, Huang C, Li F, Zhou X (2014) A versatile system for functional analysis of genes and microRNAs in cotton. *Plant Biotechnol J* 12:638–649. doi: 10.1111/pbi.12169
- Guo R, Yu F, Gao Z, et al (2011) GhWRKY3, a novel cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.) WRKY gene, is involved in diverse stress responses. *Mol Biol Rep* 38:49–58. doi: 10.1007/s11033-010-0076-4
- Guo Y, Cai Z, Gan S (2004) Transcriptome of Arabidopsis leaf senescence. *Plant, Cell Environ* 27:521–549. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-3040.2003.01158.x
- Guo Y, Gan S (2006) AtNAP, a NAC family transcription factor, has an important role in leaf senescence. *Plant J* 46:601–612. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-313X.2006.02723.x
- He X-J, Mu R-L, Cao W-H, et al (2005) AtNAC2, a transcription factor downstream of ethylene and auxin signaling pathways, is involved in salt stress response and lateral root development - He - 2005 - The Plant Journal - Wiley Online Library.pdf. *Plant J* 44:903–916. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-313X.2005.02575.x
- Hörtensteiner S, Feller U (2002) Nitrogen metabolism and remobilization during senescence. *J Exp Bot* 53:927–937. doi: 10.1093/jexbot/53.370.927

- Hu B, Jin J, Guo A-Y, et al (2015) GSDDS 2.0: an upgraded gene feature visualization server. *Bioinformatics* 31:1296–7. doi: 10.1093/bioinformatics/btu817
- Hu H, You J, Fang Y, et al (2008) Characterization of transcription factor gene SNAC2 conferring cold and salt tolerance in rice. *Plant Mol Biol* 67:169–181. doi: 10.1007/s11103-008-9309-5
- Hunter DA, Reid MS (2001) A SIMPLE AND RAPID METHOD FOR ISOLATING HIGH QUALITY RNA. *95616:147–152*.
- Kato H, Motomura T, Komeda Y, et al (2010) Overexpression of the NAC transcription factor family gene ANAC036 results in a dwarf phenotype in *Arabidopsis thaliana*. *J Plant Physiol* 167:571–577. doi: 10.1016/j.jplph.2009.11.004
- Kikuchi K, Ueguchi-Tanaka M, Yoshida KT, et al (2000) Molecular analysis of the NAC gene family in rice. *Mol Gen Genet* 262:1047–1051. doi: 10.1007/PL00008647
- Kim EH, Kim YS, Park S-H, et al (2009) Methyl Jasmonate Reduces Grain Yield by Mediating Stress Signals to Alter Spikelet Development in Rice. *Plant Physiol* 149:1751–1760. doi: 10.1104/pp.108.134684
- Kong X, Luo Z, Dong H, et al (2013) Gene Expression Profiles Deciphering Leaf Senescence Variation between Early- and Late-Senescence Cotton Lines. *PLoS One* 8:e69847. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0069847
- Li Z, Peng J, Wen X, Guo H (2012) Gene Network Analysis and Functional Studies of Senescence-associated Genes Reveal Novel Regulators of *Arabidopsis* Leaf Senescence. *J Integr Plant Biol* 54:526–539. doi: 10.1111/j.1744-7909.2012.01136.x
- Liang C, Wang Y, Zhu Y, et al (2014) OsNAP connects abscisic acid and leaf senescence by fine-tuning abscisic acid biosynthesis and directly targeting senescence-associated genes in rice. *Proc Natl Acad Sci U S A* 111:10013–8. doi: 10.1073/pnas.1321568111
- Lim PO, Kim HJ, Gil Nam H (2007) Leaf Senescence. *Annu Rev Plant Biol* 58:115–136. doi: 10.1146/annurev.arplant.57.032905.105316
- Lin JF, Wu SH (2004) Molecular events in senescing *Arabidopsis* leaves. *Plant J* 39:612–628. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-313X.2004.02160.x
- Lin R, Zhao W, Meng X, et al (2007) Rice gene OsNAC19 encodes a novel NAC-domain transcription factor and responds to infection by *Magnaporthe grisea*. *Plant Sci* 172:120–130. doi: 10.1016/j.plantsci.2006.07.019
- Liu YL, Schiff M, Dinesh-Kumar SP (2002) Virus-induced gene silencing in tomato. *Plant J* 31:777–786. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-313X.2005.02441.x
- Livak KJ, Schmittgen TD (2001) Analysis of relative gene expression data using real-time quantitative PCR and the 2^{(-Delta Delta C(T))} Method. *Methods* 25:402–8. doi: 10.1006/meth.2001.1262
- Mao X, Chen S, Li A, et al (2014) Novel NAC transcription factor TaNAC67 confers enhanced multi-abiotic stress tolerances in *Arabidopsis*. *PLoS One* 9:e84359. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0084359

- Meng C, Cai C, Zhang T, Guo W (2009) Characterization of six novel NAC genes and their responses to abiotic stresses in *Gossypium hirsutum* L. *Plant Sci* 176:352–359. doi: 10.1016/j.plantsci.2008.12.003
- Meng Q, Zhang C, Gai J, Yu D (2007) Molecular cloning, sequence characterization and tissue-specific expression of six NAC-like genes in soybean (*Glycine max* (L.) Merr.). *J Plant Physiol* 164:1002–1012. doi: 10.1016/j.jplph.2006.05.019
- Mitsuda N, Iwase A, Yamamoto H, et al (2007) NAC Transcription Factors, NST1 and NST3, Are Key Regulators of the Formation of Secondary Walls in Woody Tissues of Arabidopsis. *Plant Cell Online* 19:270–280. doi: 10.1105/tpc.106.047043
- Morris K, MacKerness S a, Page T, et al (2000) Salicylic acid has a role in regulating gene expression during leaf senescence. *Plant J* 23:677–685. doi: 10.1046/j.1365-313x.2000.00836.x
- Nakashima K, Takasaki H, Mizoi J, et al (2012) NAC transcription factors in plant abiotic stress responses. *Biochim Biophys Acta - Gene Regul Mech* 1819:97–103. doi: 10.1016/j.bbagr.2011.10.005
- Ning Y-Q, Ma Z-Y, Huang H-W, et al (2015) Two novel NAC transcription factors regulate gene expression and flowering time by associating with the histone demethylase JMJ14. *Nucleic Acids Res* 43:1469–1484. doi: 10.1093/nar/gku1382
- Ooka H, Ooka H, Satoh K, et al (2003) Comprehensive Analysis of NAC Family Genes in. *Analysis* 247:239–247.
- Peng H, Cheng H-Y, Chen C, et al (2009) A NAC transcription factor gene of Chickpea (*Cicer arietinum*), CarNAC3, is involved in drought stress response and various developmental processes. *J Plant Physiol* 166:1934–1945. doi: 10.1016/j.jplph.2009.05.013
- Peng H, Yu X, Cheng H, et al (2010) Cloning and Characterization of a Novel NAC Family Gene CarNAC1 from Chickpea (*Cicer arietinum* L.). *Mol Biotechnol* 44:30–40. doi: 10.1007/s12033-009-9202-8
- Permingeat HR, Romagnoli M V, Vallejos RH (1998) A simple method for isolating high yield and quality DNA from cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.) leaves. *Plant Mol Biol Report* 16:1–6. doi: 10.1023/A:1007466522028
- Puranik S, Sahu PP, Srivastava PS, Prasad M (2012) NAC proteins: regulation and role in stress tolerance. *Trends Plant Sci* 17:369–381. doi: Doi 10.1016/J.Tplants.2012.02.004
- Rao M V, Lee H, Creelman R a, et al (2000) Jasmonic acid signaling modulates ozone-induced hypersensitive cell death. *Plant Cell* 12:1633–1646. doi: 10.1105/tpc.12.9.1633
- Shah ST, Pang C, Hussain A, et al (2014) Molecular cloning and functional analysis of NAC family genes associated with leaf senescence and stresses in *Gossypium hirsutum* L. *Plant Cell, Tissue Organ Cult* 117:167–186. doi: 10.1007/s11240-014-0430-7
- Souer E, van Houwelingen A, Kloos D, et al (1996) The No Apical Meristem Gene of *Petunia* Is Required for Pattern Formation in Embryos and Flowers and Is Expressed at Meristem and Primordia Boundaries. *Cell* 85:159–170. doi: 10.1016/S0092-8674(00)81093-4

- Sun L, Zhang H, Li D, et al (2013) Functions of rice NAC transcriptional factors, ONAC122 and ONAC131, in defense responses against *Magnaporthe grisea*. *Plant Mol Biol* 81:41–56. doi: 10.1007/s11103-012-9981-3
- Tamura K, Dudley J, Nei M, Kumar S (2007) MEGA4: Molecular Evolutionary Genetics Analysis (MEGA) Software Version 4.0. *Mol Biol Evol* 24:1596–1599. doi: 10.1093/molbev/msm092
- Ülker B, Shahid Mukhtar M, Somssich IE (2007) The WRKY70 transcription factor of *Arabidopsis* influences both the plant senescence and defense signaling pathways. *Planta* 226:125–137. doi: 10.1007/s00425-006-0474-y
- Weaver LM, Gan S, Quirino B, Amasino RM (1998) A comparison of the expression patterns of several senescence-associated genes in response to stress and hormone treatment. *Plant Mol Biol* 37:455–469. doi: 10.1023/A:1005934428906
- Yang S-D, Seo PJ, Yoon H-K, Park C-M (2011) The *Arabidopsis* NAC Transcription Factor VNI2 Integrates Abscisic Acid Signals into Leaf Senescence via the COR/RD Genes. *Plant Cell* 23:2155–2168. doi: 10.1105/tpc.111.084913
- Zeevaert J a D, Creelman R a (1988) Metabolism and Physiology of Abscisic Acid. *Annu Rev Plant Physiol Plant Mol Biol* 39:439–473. doi: 10.1146/annurev.pp.39.060188.002255
- Zhang H, Zhou C (2013) Signal transduction in leaf senescence. *Plant Mol Biol* 82:539–545. doi: 10.1007/s11103-012-9980-4
- Zhao F, Ma J, Li L, et al (2015) GhNAC12, a neutral candidate gene, leads to early aging in cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L). *Gene*. doi: 10.1016/j.gene.2015.10.042